

Purification of ZFYVE9C (SARA) and association testing with type I and type II receptors.

Rationale:

ZFYVE9C is a scaffold protein associated with TGF β signalling. It contains a Domain of Unknown Function (DUF) for which the structure is known but the function is not. This experiment is to begin looking at the association of ZFYVE9C with ALK5 and TGFBR2 in the phosphorylated and un-phosphorylated states.

Aim:

Purify ZFYVE9CACVR2, Alk3 and Alk6 for use in crystallography studies.

Proteins to be purified:

ZFYVE9C-c009

MHHHHHHSSGVDLGTENLYFQ/*SMNLIPEDGLPPILISTGVKGDYAVEEKPSQISVMQQLEDGGPDPLVFLNA
NLLSMVKIVNYVNRKCWCFTTKGMHAVGQSEIVILLQCLPDEKCLPKDIFNHFVQLYRDALAGNVVSNLGHSSFSQ
SFLGSKEHGGFLYVTSTYQSLQDLVLPPTPYLFGILIQKWETPWAKVFPIRLMLRLGAEYRLYPCPLFSVFRKPLFGE
TGHTIMNLLADFRNYQYTLPPVQGLVVDMEVRKTSIKIPSNRYNEMMKAMNKSNEHVLGAGACFNEKADSHLVC
VQNDDGNYQTQAI SIHNQPRKVTGASFFVFSGALKSSSGYLAKSSIVEDGVMVQITAENMDSLRLALREMKDFTIT
CGKADAEPEQEHIIHQWVDDDKNVSKGVVSPIDGKSMETITNVKIFHGSEYKANGKVIRWTEVFFLENDQHNCL
SDPADHSRLTEHVAKAFCLALCPHLKLLKEDGMTKGLRVTLDSDQVGYQAGSNGQPLPSQYMNDLDSALVPVIH
GGACQLSEGPVVMELIFYILENIV

/* indicates TEV cleavage site.

TGFBR1 and TGFBR2 from previously purified protein stocks stored in -80.

TGFBR1-c003

MGHHHHHHSSGVDLGTENLYFQ/*SMEDPSLDRPFISEGTTKDLIYDMTTSGSGSGLPLLQRTIARTIVLQESIGK
GRFGEVWRGKWRGEEVAVKIFSSREERSWFREAEIYQTVMLRHENILGFIAADNKDNGTWTQLWLVS DYHEHGS
LFDYLNRYTVTVEGMIKALSTASGLAHLHMEIVGTQGKPAIAHRDLKSKNILVKKNGTCCIADLGLAVRHDSATDTI
DIAPNHRVGTKRYMAPEVLDD SINMKHFESFKRADIYAMGLVFWEIARRCSIGGIHEDYQLPYYDLVPSDPSVEEM
RKVVCEQKLRPNIPNRWQSCEALRVMKIMRECWYANGAARLTALRIKKTLSQLSQEGIKM

TGFBR2-c038

MGHHHHHHSSGVDLGTENLYFQ/*SMGEIAALEKEIAALEKEAALEKANNINHNTELLPIELDTLVGKGRFAEVYKA
KLKQNTSEQFETVAVKIFPYEYASWKTEKDIFSDINLKHENILQFLTAERKTEL GKQYWLITAFHAKGNLQEYLTRH
VISWEDLRKLGSSSLARGIAHLSDHTPCGRPKMPIVHRDLKSSNILVKNDLTCLCLDFGLSLRLDPTLSVDDLANSQG

VG TARYMAPEVLES RMNLENVESFKQTDVYSMALVLWEMTSRCNAVGEVKDYEPFPGSKVREHPCVESMKDNV
LRDRGRPEIPSWLNLHQGIQMV CETLTECWDHDPEARLTAQCVAERFSELEHLDR L

Expression:

ZFYVE9C was expressed in LB media or TB media. Overnight cultures were grown at 37°C while shaking from glycerol stock in presence of Kanamycin. Media was inoculated with 10ml/l overnight and grown for 4h before induction with 0.4M IPTG. Temperature was reduced to 18°C and left to grow overnight. Cells were harvested next morning at 5000rpm for 15 minutes. Pellets were resuspended in binding buffer (5mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, 50mM HEPES pH 7.5, 500mM NaCl) and frozen at -20°C.

Two pellets were purified separately – one from an LB pellet and one from a TB pellet. Expression had happened two years ago and thus it was unclear if either pellet had suffered degradation in that time. Each pellet was purified separately to ensure fidelity of protein.

Purification:

- Thaw pellets in luke warm water
- Sonicate all samples for 5 min (5 on, 10 off) on ice.
- Divide each sample into two centrifugation tubes and top up with 'binding buffer' (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 5mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5) so each tube is full (approx 40ml per tube).
- Add 1ml PEI (5%) per tube to precipitate DNA.
- Spin at 21 k rpm for 1 hour.
- Incubate lysate with 2ml pre-equilibrated Ni-NTA beads at 4°C for 45 min. (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 5mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5)
- Spin down beads at 700g for 10 minutes to separate beads from lysate.
- Pour off lysate.
- Resuspend beads in 50ml binding buffer and load onto gravity flow column (collect flow through)
- Wash with 30ml wash buffer (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 30mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5).
- Elute in 7ml elution buffer 1 (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 50mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5).
- Elute in 3 x 7ml elution buffer 4 (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 250mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5).
- Run samples on an SDS PAGE gel (mix 5ul of loading dye with 15ul sample, boil for 3 minutes and load 10ul onto the gel.) and run at 160V for 50 minutes.

SDS-PAGE gel of Nickle purification of ZFYVE9C (LB) and ZFYVE9C (TB) showing flow through, washes 1 and 2 and four elution fractions.

- Pool fractions elution fractions E1 - E4(1) for each protein and add Tev protease and leave overnight at 4C.
- Concentrate down samples to <5ml and run on a pre-equilibrated GF 75 column using standard gel filtration buffer (300mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 5mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5).
- Collect fractions and run a gel of the peaks. All gels are 4 – 12% gradient commercial gradient gels run for 50 minutes at 170V.

SDS-PAGE (top) and UV traces from gel filtration 75 column purification runs. LB expression on the left and TB expression on the right.

- Use mass spec to confirm protein identity. Sample from LB is correct. Sample from TB is the wrong size so discard protein and use LB sample with correct mass for future experiments.

Mass spec of both protein samples shows that ZFYVE9C from LB (top) is the correct mass while ZFYVE9C from TB (bottom) is the wrong mass.

ZFYVE9C and TGBFR1 and TGFBR2 complex formation:

- Thaw out samples of TGFBR1 and TGFBR2 from pre-purified stocks in the -80 freezer.
- Split each sample in half and incubate one half of each receptor for 30 min with 0.5mM ATP and 5mM Mg²⁺ to phosphorylate it.
- Mix 1/2 of ZFYVE9C sample with excess un-phosphorylated TGFBR1 and phosphorylated TGFBR1 receptor respectively and concentrate down using a 50kDa MWCO spin concentrator (spin at 4000 rpm at 15 minute intervals) to <5ml. Run each sample separately on a GF75 column to look for shifts in elution profile.

SDS-PAGE gels and associated uv traces from GF75 column showing no association between ZFYVE9C and TGFBR1 (unphos on left and phos on right).

- No association observed so take unbound ZFYVE9C and repeat with TGFBR2 and phos TGFBR2 to look for complex formation.

SDS-PAGE gels and associated uv traces from GF75 column showing no association between ZFYVE9C and TGFBR2 (unphos on left and phos on right).

- No association observed here either so any complex formed is insufficiently tight to be seen by gel filtration.

Summary plot of elution profile of ZFYVE9C alone and mixed with either TGFBR1 (Phos and un-phos) or TGRBR2 (Phos and un-phos) showing no peak shift for the ZFYVE9C (SARA) protein and thus no complex formation detectible by Gel Filtration.